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Standards of comparison and the case of Spanish “*que - de* alternation”

Laura Vela-Plo

This paper offers a formal syntactic and semantic analysis of standards of comparison in Spanish, in addition to presenting a parametric analysis that accounts for the variation in standards of comparison cross-linguistically. Two independent parameters are argued to account for the properties of standards of comparison in languages typologically as diverse as Spanish, English, Japanese or Turkish: (i) a syntactic parameter, by which either phrasal, or both phrasal and clausal structures are allowed in the complement position of the standard marker; and (ii) a revised semantic parameter that restricts the semantic type of the standard.

1. Introduction

The syntactic and semantic properties of comparative structures are still a topic of great debate. In order to examine comparative structures as a whole, we need a deeper understanding of the individual pieces that compose the puzzle that comparatives represent. For this reason, the focus of this paper lies on one of the main components of these structures: the standard of comparison.

The standard of comparison sets the reference from which the target of comparison is described. In a simple sentence like (1), for instance, Ana is the target of the comparison; she is being compared to Jon (the standard of comparison) with respect to their individual levels of intelligence, and Jon’s level of intelligence has been set as the referent for the comparison.

(1) Ana is smarter than Jon.

How is it that we come to interpret a standard of comparison such as ‘Jon’ as Jon’s maximum level of intelligence? And more importantly for our concerns here, how can we derive a compositional analysis that accounts for the syntactic and semantic properties of standards of comparison? What are the constraints that apply to standards of comparison cross-linguistically? These are the main concerns that this paper sets out to address. By answering these questions, we will be able to determine the limits of the cross-linguistic variation in standards of comparison, as well as to lay down the first piece of the puzzle on comparative structures.

The main claim endorsed in this paper is that two independent parameters¹ are necessary to account for the properties of standards of comparison cross-linguistically: a syntactic one, namely the licensing of a [-/+ CLAUSAL] structure, as previously proposed in the literature; and a revised semantic parameter, which lies in the possibility to license [-/+ DEGREE] denoting standards.

In Sections 1.1 and 1.2 I will review some of the most recent literature and analyses on the syntactic and semantic points of variation in standards of comparison. In Section 2, I will examine the syntactic and semantic properties of standards of comparison in a specific Romance language, Spanish. This language is especially interesting for the purposes of this research because the types of standards of comparison present in this language *prima facie* seem to be compatible with the syntactic and semantic variation patterns that have been proposed so far. However, we will see that the semantic analyses that we can find in the literature cannot account for the whole comparative paradigm in this language and that some refinements are necessary. Hence, in Section 3, I will provide a novel semantic description and classification of standards of comparison in Spanish (which will be classified in three main types; Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3). Finally, in Section 3.4 I will show how the analysis of the properties of standards of comparison in Spanish fits in with the cross-linguistic classification and parametric description of these phenomena.

An additional outcome of the analysis of Spanish inequality comparatives and the ‘*que-de* alternation’ examined in this paper is that, at least in Spanish, the sense of comparison in a comparative structure is contingent on both the presence of a comparative marker (*más* ‘more’) and the choice of standard marker (*que* ‘that’ or *de* ‘of, from’).

1.1. Previous syntactic analyses

The syntactic properties of standards of comparison are subject to important cross-linguistic variation.

On the one hand, some languages only allow phrasal arguments in the complement position of the standard marker. I will be using the label [- CLAUSAL] for those standards of comparison that do not seem to be propositional. Languages such as Turkish (Hofstetter 2009, see (2)), Japanese (Beck et al. 2004, Sudo 2015), Mandarin (Fu 1978; Xiang 2003), or Hindi-Urdu (Bhatt & Takahashi 2008), for example, do not allow this type of clausal, CP arguments in the complement position of their standard marker unless they are embedded under a nominal in a relative clause (RC)² or nominalized, as in the example in (2c).

- (2) a. Maria Peter'den hızlı koştu. (Turkish; Hofstetter 2009:189-190)
 Maria Peter.ABL fast run.PST.3SG
 ‘Maria ran faster than Peter.’

¹ Throughout this paper, parameters are regarded as feature specifications on lexical items that vary within languages and derivations, arguably on the standard marker that introduces the standard of comparison, rather than parameters which globally define a language in the sense of the Principles and Parameters framework (cf. Eguren, Soriano & Mendikoetxea 2016, for a recent review on this topic). Thus, parameters are not considered binary switches that determine whether a particular language allows a syntactic structure or not. As will be seen later in the descriptions of the languages examined in this paper, and as it is summarized in Tables 2 & 3, both parametric options might be active within a language.

² I will be assuming that a RC under a nominal head is still a phrasal argument (a nominal with a clausal modifier).

- b. *Maria Peter'den (hızlı) koştu hızlı koştu.
 Maria Peter.ABL (fast) run.PST.3SG fast run.PST.3SG
 Intended: ‘Maria ran faster than Peter ran.’
- c. Maria benim düşündüğümden zengin.
 Maria my think.PTCP.1SG.ABL rich
 ‘Maria is richer than I thought.’

On the other hand, some languages allow their standard markers to take both phrasal and clausal complements [-/+ CLAUSAL]. These are languages such as English (Heim 1985; Kennedy 1999, a.o.), Spanish (Brucart 2003), Italian, Hungarian and Russian (Bacskai-Atkari 2014). The sentence in (3) shows an example of a phrasal standard in English, in which clausal expansion is not permitted. In this case, the complement of the standard marker *than* is a Measure Phrase (MP) of a [- CLAUSAL] nature.

- (3) This mountain is higher than 1200 meters (*are/*is). / MP [- CLAUSAL]

In contrast with (3), the example in (4) licenses a standard that allows clausal expansion: *than Jon is*. The reduced version of (4), *than Jon*, could be thus analysed either as having an underlying clausal structure to which a deletion process has applied (a *reduction* analysis; cf. (5)); or as involving a phrasal standard (a *direct* analysis; cf. (5b)). Within reductionist analyses, the underlying structure of (4a) has been represented as in (5a) since Chomsky (1977), with movement of a degree operator (similar to a *wh*-movement) to the left periphery of the clause and deletion of all redundant material, the gradable predicate in this case (also known as *comparative deletion*).

- (4) a. Ana is smarter than Jon (is).
 b. Ana is smarter than him (*is).
- (5) a. ...than [CP *Op_i* Jon is *d_i* smart] [+ CLAUSAL]
 b. ...than [DP him]³ [- CLAUSAL]

The sentence in (4b), in contrast, is apparently phrasal, since the standard of comparison does not surface with the case mark that corresponds to the subject of an inflected clause, as could be expected under the deletion analysis. Furthermore, the alternative with clausal expansion leads to unacceptability. Hence, a *direct* analysis, namely a *what-you-see-is-what-you-get* interpretation, is available, which could potentially be represented as in (5b).

Moreover, the example in (6) is a comparative sentence with a clearly clausal standard in English, also called *subcomparative*. It is common practice to analyse these cases as also involving degree operator movement to the left periphery of its clause (5b), just as in (4a).

- (6) a. This table is longer than that door is (wide).
 b. This table is longer than [CP *Op_i* that door is *d_i* wide] [+ CLAUSAL]

³ Hankamer (1973), Napoli (1983) and Kennedy (1999), among others, argue for a direct analysis as represented in (5b). Even though a direct analysis would be the most straightforward analysis, it might not be the only analysis for (4b). See Pancheva (2006) for an alternative analysis involving a small clause. For the necessary application of the direct analysis in comparatives in other languages, such as Hindi-Urdu, see Bhatt & Takahashi (2007, 2011).

In sum, the first difference that we observe with respect to the syntactic properties of the standard of comparison has to do with the nature of the complement of the standard, and in particular, with whether both phrasal and clausal complements are licensed in this position, or whether only phrasal complements are. We could translate this point of variation observed within and across languages as a [-/+CLAUSAL] parameter.

1.2. Previous semantic analyses

The standard of comparison has traditionally been represented semantically as a type of definite description that denotes a maximal degree (von Stechow 1984, Rullmann 1995). Hence, within the traditional analysis of standards of comparison it is common to assume that comparatives with a clausal standard such as (6a) above are degree-denoting (see e.g. Bresnan 1973; von Stechow 1984; Bhatt & Pancheva 2004). This degree is mapped onto a scale, an abstract representation that can be used to measure and compare objects with respect to a particular gradable property (Kennedy 2006, Bale 2008).

Nonetheless, some authors have argued that in addition to degree-denoting standards (type *d*), there are also cases of comparisons of individuals in which the standard of comparison exhibits a referential definite that denotes an individual (Hoeksema 1983; Heim 1985; Kennedy 1999, 2007; Bhatt & Takahashi 2007, 2011), represented by the semantic type *e*. For instance, Kennedy (2007) argues that Japanese has only individual comparison, and thus, that all standards of comparison in this language are DPs (either simple DPs that are individual-denoting as in (6a) or complex DPs modified by a RC that are degree-denoting) that denote individuals. Shimoyama (2012:85, fn 3) argued in favour of the weaker claim that says that both degree and individual-denoting standards are available in Japanese by showing that the Japanese standard marker *yori* can take the name of a degree (a Measure Phrase) as its complement (see (7b)).

(7) Japanese

- a. Taroo-wa *Hanako* yori takusan(-no) hon-o katta.
 Taroo-TOP Hanako than many(-GEN) book-ACC bought
 ‘Taroo bought more books than Hanako.’
- b. Kono mati-de-wa *gozyuu-meetoru*-yori takai biru-wa kinsisareteiru.
 this town-in-TOP fifty-meters-than high building-TOP prohibited
 In this town, buildings higher than 50 meters are prohibited.

This proposal has been supported by Bhatt & Takahashi (2007, 2011). These authors also offer several arguments supporting the view that both types of standards are also available in Hindi-Urdu: degree-denoting ones such as ‘three’ in sentence (8b) and individual-denoting standards such as ‘Bill’ in (8a).⁴

(8) Hindi-Urdu

- a. John *Bill*-se zyaadaa lambaa hai.
 John Bill-than more tall is
 ‘John is taller than Bill.’

⁴ The reader should refer to the original papers for evidence supporting the argument that cases such as (8a) cannot be analysed as degree-denoting standards in disguise by appealing to a reduced clause analysis.

- b. Atif-ne *tiin*-se zyaadaa kitaabē khariid-ii thī:
 Atif-ERG three-than more books.F buy-PFV.f be.PST.FPI.
 ‘Atif bought more than three books.’

In order to account for the Japanese contrast, Kennedy (2007) proposes a degree versus individual-denoting standard analysis (adaptation of Kennedy 2007, based on the work by Beck et al. 2004):

- (9) a. $\llbracket \text{more}_{\text{degree}} \rrbracket = \lambda G_{\langle e,d \rangle} \lambda d_d \lambda x_e [G(x) > d]$ (7b)
 b. $\llbracket \text{more}_{\text{individual}} \rrbracket = \lambda G_{\langle e,d \rangle} \lambda y_e \lambda x_d [G(x) > G(y)]$ (7a)

Sentence (7b) would be analysed as in (9a), with a standard that denotes a degree directly; whereas the representation in (9b) would be applied to individual standards such as the one in (7a). These types of standards express orderings between arbitrary individuals, and the degree of the standard is derived by applying the meaning of the gradable predicate (the base of comparison) to the two individuals that are being compared. Eventually, standards are of type *d* in both cases.

Bhatt & Takahashi (2007, 2011) follow a similar strategy to account for the variation observed in Hindi-Urdu standards of comparison (cf. (8)) and also posit two ‘more’s: one taking standards of type *d* and the other taking type *e* standards (2-place and 3-place ‘more’).

Summarizing, the second attested point of variation in standards of comparison has to do with the denotation of the complement of the standard marker, and in particular, with the possibility of having degree and individual-denoting standards. We could translate this point of variation as a [DEGREE]/[INDIVIDUAL] semantic parameter.

In the next section, I will examine inequality comparatives in Spanish and introduce the *que-de* alternation that will be discussed in this paper. Building on previous analyses of Spanish comparatives and on some novel observations, I will show that the semantic parameter proposed in the literature is insufficient to account for the whole comparative paradigm in Spanish. On this basis, I will thus propose some refinements to this parameter and a new classification of Spanish comparatives. Finally, I will offer a compositional analysis of inequality comparatives in Spanish and a parametric classification that accounts for the cross-linguistic variation on standards of comparison in Section 3.

2. Spanish “que-de alternation” and some novel observations

Comparative structures in Spanish are especially interesting due to the variation that we find in this language. Specifically, there are two possibilities available in Spanish comparatives to introduce the referent of the comparison, namely the standard: the complementizer or conjunction *que* (‘that’) or the preposition *de* (‘of, from’).

According to the literature, *de* standards confront comparable “magnitudes” (either degrees or quantities), and have an obligatorily quantitative nature (Martínez 1987, Gutiérrez Ordóñez 1994, Romero Cambrón 1998). In contrast, *que* standards do not have a quantificational base; rather, they primarily represent individuals or properties (Brucart 2003, 2009). This contrast is illustrated in (10) and (11).

- (10) a. Mide más { *que /de } dos metros.
measure more than_{que}/than_{de} two meters
'It measures more than_{de} two meters.'
- b. Mide más { que /*de } Ana.
measure more than_{que}/than_{de} Ana
'It measures more than_{que} Ana'.
- (11) a. Jon comió más que un dinosaurio.⁵
Jon ate more than a dinosaur
'Jon ate more than_{que} a dinosaur (would eat).'
- b. Jon comió más de un dinosaurio.
Jon ate more than a dinosaur
'Jon ate more than_{de} one dinosaur.' (maybe 2 or 3 dinosaurs)

In (10a), we observe that when the standard of comparison denotes a degree, as in the MP 'two meters', a *de* standard is the only acceptable option; while in (10b), the individual denoting standard *Ana* has to be introduced by *que*.⁶

The minimal pair in (11a)-(11b) illustrates a similar contrast. In (11), I have given an example which illustrates the different roles of *que* and *de* in the standard of comparison and which is particularly interesting due to the ambiguous nature of *un* between the indefinite 'a' and the numeral 'one'. In the comparative with the *que* standard, the quantity eaten by two individual referents is compared ((11a), *Figure 1*), and *un dinosaurio* is interpreted as an indefinite referent, 'a dinosaur'; whereas in the case of the standard with *de* the article *un* has to be translated as the numeral 'one', 'than one dinosaur', alluding to the quantity of eaten elements ((11b), *Figure 2*).

Figure 1: Interpretation of (11).

Figure 2: Interpretation of (11).

Moreover, *de* standards cannot take clausal complements unless they are embedded in a relative clause without antecedent, as shown by the contrast in (12a)-(12b) (in fact, *de*

⁵ This sentence could also have the meaning 'Jon ate more than_{que} a dinosaur.' (something qualitatively different, 'other than a dinosaur'), if *more* were focalized. That is, both a subject or object interpretation of the indefinite referent 'a dinosaur' are possible in (10a).

⁶ Whether we need a direct or a reductionist analysis of the standard in sentences (9b) and (10b) is not a crucial distinction at this point. For now, we are interested in the distribution of *que* and *de* standards. The first observation is that *que* is not allowed with degree-denoting standards, but *de* is. The second observation is that the standard marker *de* cannot directly take what in the surface looks as an individual-denoting element, while this is allowed with *que*.

In what follows, I will focus on inequality comparatives that present standards that are obviously clausal (for example, (19) below) or comparatives with phrasal standards for which there is enough evidence for a direct phrasal analysis (as in sentences (12) and (13), for instance).

standards are known as ‘relative comparatives’ in traditional grammars of Spanish; Gutiérrez Ordóñez 1994, Romero Cambrón 1998, Sáez 1999, Brucart 2003, 2009, a.o.). No such restriction is found in *que* standards (see (13); cf. Gutiérrez Ordóñez 1994, on the possibilities when having a standard with *que* in Spanish).

- (12) a. *Ana ha conseguido más libros para el colegio de Jon necesita.
 Ana has obtained more books for the school than Jon needs
 Intended: ‘Ana got more books for school than_{de} Jon needs.’
- b. Ana ha conseguido más libros para el colegio de los que Jon necesita.
 Ana has obtained more books for the school than the.PL that Jon needs
 ‘Ana got more books for school than_{de} Jon needs.’
- (13) Ana ha conseguido más libros para el colegio que trabajos ha pedido su profesor.
 Ana has obtained more books for the school than essays has asked her teacher
 ‘Ana got more books for school than_{que} her teacher ordered essays.’

Taking previous analyses into consideration, we would expect the pattern in (14).

- (14) Potential analysis of Spanish standards of comparison (to be revised):
- A. *de* standards: [DEGREE] [-CLAUSAL]
- B. *que* standards: [INDIVIDUAL] [-CLAUSAL] or [DEGREE] [+CLAUSAL]

However, as I will show now, the semantic characterization of comparatives proposed in Section 1.2. is insufficient to capture the properties of Spanish comparatives: the picture is more complex than what the traditional analyses predict. This is so because we find cases that do not conform to the semantic [INDIVIDUAL]/[DEGREE] distinction, since (i) they do not involve a directly degree-denoting standard (via a MP as in (3) or degree abstraction as in (5a) or (6)), and further (ii) they are not individual-denoting standards (*e* type, as in (4b)) either.

2.2. More *N* than *N* comparatives

Consider the examples in (15) and (16). Sáez (1992) suggests that standards of comparison such as *que hombres* ‘than men’ in (15) could be analysed as phrasal standards. Brucart (2003) also picks up on this point and argues in favour of Sáez’s proposal. As we will see next, I will go a step further and propose that sentences like (15) and (16) in Spanish involve phrasal standards in which, crucially, the complement of the standard marker *que* does not conform to the semantic parameter previously described in the literature. These standards are [-CLAUSAL], and consequently, do not involve degree abstraction. They neither denote degrees directly (they are not measure phrases or degree phrases) nor a referential (*e* type) individual. I will refer to inequality comparatives like (15) and (16) as *more N than N* comparatives.

- (15) Más mujeres [que *hombres*] fueron a la manifestación.
 More women [than men] went to the march.
 ‘More women than_{que} men attended the march.’

- (16) La huelga contra la LOMCE arrastra a más alumnos [que profesores].⁷
 the strike against the LOMCE drags DOM more students [than teachers]
 ‘The strike against the LOMCE drags more students than_{que} teachers.’

The acceptability of (15) contrasts with (17a), where the standard is clearly clausal. Clausal standards in Spanish cannot be linearized in a position between the subject and the verb of the matrix clause (see (17a-b)). The contrast in grammaticality between (15) and (17a) will lead us to defend a phrasal analysis for the standard in (15).

- (17) a. *Ayer, más mujeres [que hombres (fueron) la semana pasada] fueron a
 yesterday more women [than men went the week past] went to
 la manifestación.
 the march.
 Lit. ‘Yesterday, more women than men (attended) last week attended the march.’
 b. Ayer, más mujeres fueron a la manifestación [que hombres (fueron)
 yesterday more women went to the march [than men went
 la semana pasada].
 the week past]
 ‘Yesterday, more women attended the march than men (did) last week.’

Furthermore, note that not just any phrasal element can act as a standard and be linearized between the subject and the verb of a clause, as (18a-b) show. In these sentences, the complement of the standard marker is a temporal adverb, possibly modifying a verb that has been elided due to identity with the verb in the matrix clause. Thus, (18b) might be a case of a reduced clausal standard which looks phrasal on the surface due to elision of some material within the clause.

- (18) a. *Hoy más mujeres [que ayer] han ido a la manifestación.
 todaymore women [than yesterday] have gone to the march
 Lit: ‘Today more women than_{que} yesterday have attended the march.’
 b. Hoy más mujeres han ido a la manifestación [que ayer].
 today more women have gone to the march [than yesterday]
 ‘Today more women have attended the march than_{que} yesterday.’

What we learn from the contrast between (17) and the ungrammatical (18a) is that the ban on clausal standards being linearized between the subject and the verb of the matrix clause is not due to a constraint that only allows simple, phrasal standards in that position, but to a ban on any type of clausal standards (reduced and unreduced) in subject positions.

The schematic bracketing proposed for (12=19a), is presented in (19b):

- (19) a. Más mujeres que hombres fueron a la manifestación. [- CLAUSAL]
 More women than men went to the march.

⁷ Headline from an article in El Diario Montañés (09-03-2017)
 <<http://www.eldiariomontanes.es/cantabria/201703/08/convocantes-huelga-educativa-llaman-20170308211154.html>>

- ‘More women than_{que} men attended the march.’
 b. [DP Más mujeres [_{thanP} que hombres]]

Furthermore, *more N than N* comparatives such as (19) in Spanish present two other interesting properties, which have gone unnoticed in the literature: (i) they are not restricted to subject positions only; and (ii) they are subject to an adjacency restriction between the element modified by the comparative marker *más* and the standard of comparison. These two properties are exemplified in (13), repeated below as (20a). In (20a), the comparative marker *más* is modifying the bare plural *alumnos*, the object of the sentence, which is introduced by the preposition *a*.⁸ In this case, the standard of comparison is the NP *profesores*. If we extrapose the standard and introduce some adjuncts between the modified nominal and the standard as in (20b), the use of the DOM marking preposition becomes obligatory. This adjacency restriction supports the bracketing proposal in (20c) and the general schematic analysis proposed for these structures in (21).

- (20) a. La huelga contra la LOMCE arrastra[a [más alumnos [que profesores]]].
 the strike against the LOMCE drags [DOM[more students [than teachers]]]
 ‘The strike against the LOMCE drags more students than_{que} teachers.’
 b. La huelga contra la LOMCE arrastra[a más alumnos]a la calles
 the strike against the LOMCE drags [DOM more students]to the streets
 cada semana[que *(a) profesores].
 every week [than *(DOM) teachers]
 ‘The strike against the LOMCE drags more students to the streets every week
 than_{que} (it does) teachers.’
 c. [PP a [DP más [NP alumnos] [_{thanP} que [NP profesores]]]]
 d.
 (21) [DP more [NP Xs] [_{thanP} than [NP Ys]]

In sum, the properties of standards of comparison in comparatives with a structure like the one in (21) – that of sentences such as (15) and (16) – cannot be accounted for by the semantic [INDIVIDUAL]/[DEGREE] parameter, because the standards in these cases do not involve degree abstraction, nor do they denote either degrees directly (they are not a MPs), or a referential individual (they are not DPs).

2.2. Event quantification comparatives

We find another case that cannot be accounted for by previous semantic analyses in one kind of clausal comparatives in Spanish, which I will refer to as *event quantification* comparatives. First, consider the pair of comparative sentences which clearly present clausal standards with contrasting word orders in (22).

- (22) a. Jon compró más libros que Ana leyó cómics.
 Jon bought more books than Ana read comics
 ‘Jon bought more books than_{que} Ana read comics.’
 b. Jon compró más libros que cómics leyó Ana.

⁸ This is so because Spanish is a Differential Object Marking (DOM) language.

Jon bought more books than comics read Ana
 (Lit.) ‘Jon bought more books than_{que.inv} comics read Ana.

In these cases, it is clear that the standard marker *que* takes a fully clausal element in its complement position. I will argue that this word order difference is not trivial since, in fact, sentences (22a-b) present radically different syntactic and semantic properties (see *Table 1* for a summary of the differences).

- A. Sentence 0 is sensitive to coordination constraints, while 0 is not. The fact that sentences like (22a) are subject to coordination constraints was already attested by Sáez (1992) and some of his arguments will be reviewed in the following paragraphs.
- B. Both sentences have different interpretations. The (b) version with OVS word order compares the relative quantities of different sorts of objects. In (22b) in particular, the number of books is compared to the number of comics. But crucially, in the (a) version, I will argue that the relative frequencies of two types of events - the number of instances in which those events have occurred - are compared. In this case, *more* seems to quantify over number of *events* and it is thus comparing frequencies or pluralities of events. Hence, sentence (22a) has an interpretation similar to ‘There have been more instances of Jon buying books than instances of Ana reading comics’.

Comparative sentences such as (22b) are known as *subcomparatives*. According to Bresnan (1973) and many other authors after her (cf. Sáez 1992, Brucart 2003, Reglero 2007, for Spanish *subcomparatives*), the underlying representation of (22b) contains a variable ranging over amounts or degrees of cardinality. Moreover, one of the most striking properties of Spanish *subcomparatives* is their unusual surface word order, with the object (cf. (22b)) or a gradable predicate (23) first and subject-verb inversion. This inversion pattern is also present in *wh*-movement contexts, such as questions (Torrego 1984).

(23) Esta mesa es más larga que *ancha es esa puerta*.
 This table is more long than wide is that door
 ‘This table is longer than that door is wide.’

In contrast, comparatives with a clausal standard that presents the canonical word order (SVO) will be argued to conform another class of comparatives with a different underlying syntactic structure, as Sáez (1992) already suggested, and, interestingly, also to a different interpretation. There are two novel observations that, as far as I know, have not received a formal explanation in the literature on Spanish comparatives. The first is the interpretive contrast between (22a) and (22b); and the second is the fact that comparatives with a clausal standard that has the canonical word order (SVO) as in (22a) involve a comparison on the relative frequencies of two types of events, namely, the number of instances in which those events have occurred.

The interpretive difference that I am alluding to distinguishes (i) comparison of amounts of objects (degrees of cardinality) or degrees of a gradable predicate in *subcomparatives* like (22b) and (23), from (ii) comparison of number of instantiations of some events (degrees of frequency) in *event quantification* comparatives (22a). This distinction is a very subtle one. In order to check that the above intuitions are correct, we can test some predictions derived from these hypotheses.

In (24) and (25) below, two scenarios are created in which one of the interpretations (either the degree or the event quantification reading) is very salient and the second reading is quite unnatural. First, in (24), a context in which the *event quantification* interpretation is more salient is created. Here, the comparison is located at some specified interval of time, note that the verbs in the matrix clause and the standard clause are stage-level predicates (the verb *estar*) and closed-scale, absolute adjectives are employed (cf. Kennedy & McNally 2005, Gumiel & Pérez-Jiménez 2012). If in clausal comparatives with an SVX word order in the standard *more* is quantifying over number of events, then, our prediction is that in a clausal comparative with the properties of (24), the SVX word order will be preferred over an XVS one. As the acceptability contrast between (24a) and (24b) shows, this first prediction is borne out: the *event quantification* interpretation is associated to the use of an SVX word order in the standard of comparison.

- (24) a. Este mes, Jon ha estado más enfermo que *Mikel ha estado sano*.⁹
 this month Jon has been more sick than Mikel has been healthy
 ‘This month, Jon has been sick more (times) than Mikel has been healthy.’
 b. *Este mes, Jon ha estado más enfermo que *sano ha estado Mikel*.
 this month Jon has been more sick than healthy has been Mikel
 ‘Jon has been more sick than Mikel has been healthy.’

Second, in (25), the degree comparison interpretation is made more salient by using an individual-level, gradable predicate (more specifically, a open-scale, relative adjective combined with *ser*) in the standard. If the interpretation of clausal comparatives with an XVS word order in the standard is that of a comparison between two degrees associated to two different gradable adjectives, as proposed, I also predict that, in a context such as (25), an XVS word order in the standard should be preferred over the canonical SVX word order. This second prediction is also borne out, as shown by the contrast in grammaticality between (25a), with an SVX word order, and (25b), with an XVS word order.

- (25) a. *Jon es más comunista que la sangre es roja.¹⁰
 Jon is more communist than the blood is red
 ‘Jon is more communist than the blood is red.’
 b. Jon es más comunista que roja es la sangre.
 Jon is more communist than red is the blood
 ‘Jon is more communist than blood is red.’

In fact, the predicate-subject-verb word order is also preferred in typical cases of subcomparatives, as in (23), where two degrees are compared.

Summarizing, what we have seen so far is that clausal comparatives with an XVS word order compare relative quantities of different sorts of objects or degrees associated to different gradable predicates. These comparatives have been referred to as *subcomparatives*. In contrast, clausal comparatives with an SVX word order compare the number of instances

⁹ As a reviewer suggests, (24a) might also contribute a duration interpretation (‘...has been sick for a longer period of time than Mikel has been healthy.’) in addition to the event quantification interpretation. Since we are focused on understanding the contrast between (22a) and (22b), and in (22a) no such interpretation is available, I will not delve into this second reading that could be associated with (24a).

¹⁰ Thanks to Myriam Uribe-Etxebarria for offering this example.

in which two types of events have occurred. I have proposed the label *event quantification* comparatives for these latter cases.

With respect to their syntactic differences, in his 1992 paper on Spanish comparatives, Sáez already argued extensively that comparatives with an SVO clausal standard are subject to coordination constraints, whereas comparatives with an OVS standard are not. A justification of the coordination analysis immediately follows.

For limitations of space, I will only review three of Sáez's arguments that support the claims that these two types of comparatives have different syntactic structures and that comparatives like that in (19a) should be analysed as involving coordination.¹¹

First, what I am calling *event quantification* comparatives, i.e. sentences like (22a) and (24a), are subject to a constraint on extraction from the standard clause (see (26b)), but allow Across-the-Board (ATB) extraction from both clauses (see (26a)), according to Sáez (1992). On the other hand, as the author argues, *subcomparatives* such as (22b) and (23) do not present this constraint, and extraction from the standard clause is available (cf. (27)). The same restrictions that apply to *event quantification* comparatives also apply to general cases of coordination, as the sentences in (28) show.

Event quantification:

- (26) a. ¿A quién compró Pedro más manzanas _ que vendió Juan peras _ ?
 to whom bought Pedro more apples than_{que} sold Juan pears ?
 Lit. 'To whom did Pedro buy more apples _ than John sold pears _ ?'
 b. *¿A quién compró Pedro más manzanas _ que vendió Juan peras a Luis?
 to whom bought Pedro more apples _ than sold Juan pears to Luis?
 'To whom did Pedro buy more apples _ than_{que} sold Juan pears to Luis?'

Subcomparative:

- (27) ¿A quién compró Pedro más manzanas _ que peras vendió Juan a Luis?
 to whom bought Pedro more apples _ than pears sold Juan to Luis
 Lit. 'To whom did Pedro buy more apples _ than_{que} pears sold Juan to Luis?'

Coordination:

- (28) a. ¿A quién compró Pedro manzanas _ y vendió Juan peras _ ?
 to whom bought Pedro apples _ and sold Juan pears _
 Lit. 'To whom did Pedro buy apples _ and sold Juan pears _ ?'
 b. *¿A quién compró Pedro manzanas _ y vendió Juan peras a Luis?
 to whom bought Pedro apples _ and sold Juan pears to Luis
 'To whom did Pedro buy apples _ and sold Juan pears to Luis?'

Thus, in comparatives involving event quantification the standard marker *que* seems to behave as a conjunction (*que*_&) coordinating the matrix and the standard clauses, while it behaves as a preposition (*que*_{prep}) introducing an embedded clause in subcomparatives (Sáez 1992).

Second, another interesting property that distinguishes *event quantification* comparatives from *subcomparatives* in Spanish is the availability of long distance movement (Sáez 1992). *Subcomparatives* allow comparison with a standard that is deeply embedded, as is the case of 'pears' in sentence (29). Nevertheless, sentence (30) does not have the interpretation that there

¹¹ The reader is encouraged to consult Sáez (1992) for further evidence supporting this point.

were more instances of Juan buying apples than the number of instances of Luis selling pears that María thought there were.

Subcomparative:

- (29) Juan compró más manzanas que peras se piensa María que vendió Luis.
 Juan bought more apples than pears thinks María that sold Luis
 Lit. ‘Juan bought more apples than_{que} pears thinks María that sold Luis.’

Event quantification:

- (30) *Juan compró más manzanas que María se piensa que Luis vendió peras.
 Juan bought more apples than María thinks that Luis sold pears
 ‘Juan bought more apples than_{que} María thinks that Luis sold pears’.

A third piece of evidence that distinguishes these two types of comparatives in Spanish and which argues in favour of the coordination analysis of *event quantification* comparatives is the constraint on subjunctive mood shown in (31) (cf. Sáez 1992). This constraint is also present in coordinated sentences in Spanish (see (32)), but not in *subcomparative* sentences like (33), nor in comparatives in which the standard of comparison is introduced by the preposition *de*, as in the example in (34). The following examples have been slightly modified from those in Sáez’s paper in order to have the most similar possible minimal pairs.

Event quantification:

- (31) *Juan ha comprado más manzanas que Ana haya podido vender peras.
 Juan has bought more apples than Ana has_{subj} could sell pears
 ‘Juan has bought more apples than_& Ana could_{subj} sell pears.’

Coordination:

- (32) *Juan ha comprado manzanas y Ana haya podido vender peras.
 Juan has bought apples and Ana has_{subj} could sell pears
 ‘Juan has bought apples and Ana could_{subj} sell pears.’

Subcomparative:

- (33) Juan ha comprado más manzanas que peras haya podido vender Ana.
 Juan has bought more apples than pears has_{subj} could sell Ana.
 ‘Juan has bought more apples than pears could_{subj} sell Ana.’

Comparative with de_{prep} standard:

- (34) Juan compró más manzanas de las que Ana haya podido vender.
 Juan bought more apples than the that Ana has_{subj} could sell
 ‘Juan bought more apples than_{de} the ones that Ana could_{subj} sell.’

Hence, as Sáez (1992) argues, *event quantification* comparatives seem to pattern with cases of clausal coordination, and *subcomparatives* pattern with comparatives with the prepositional standard *de* and introduce an embedded clause.

The syntactic and semantic differences between the two types of comparatives with a clausal standard in Spanish are summarized in *Table 1*.

	Subcomparatives: <i>que_{prep}</i> XVS	Event quantification comparatives: <i>que</i> & SVX
Syntax	<p>As argued by Sáez (1992), <i>subcomparatives</i> do not display coordination constraint effects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ any kind of extraction ✓ long distance movement ✓ subjunctive mood <p>In the standard clause, there is <i>wh</i>-movement of the degree to the left periphery of the clause and pied-piping of the restrictor (cf. Brucart 2003). The degree abstraction is triggering the subject-verb inversion within the embedded clause.</p>	<p>As argued by Sáez (1992), the matrix and the standard clause are coordinated. These comparatives are subject to coordination constraints:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ only ATB extraction ✗ long distance movement ✗ subjunctive mood <p><u>New proposal:</u> No degree abstraction is involved in the standard clause (evidenced by the lack of subject-verb inversion in the embedded clause).</p>
Semantics	<p>In <i>subcomparatives</i>, the standard denotes a degree directly and thus degrees of some gradable predicate or degrees of cardinality (number of objects) are compared (Bresnan 1972).</p>	<p><u>New proposal:</u> <i>event quantification comparatives</i> involve comparison of frequencies or “times” of an event happening, that is, they compare the number of sub-events.</p>

Table 1: Two types of comparatives with clausal standards in Spanish

Finally, if we assume that what triggers subject-verb inversion in Spanish *subcomparatives* is *wh*-movement of a degree element to [Spec, CP], then the lack of subject-verb inversion in *event quantification* comparatives should be interpreted as reflecting the fact that they do not involve degree abstraction. This hypothesis is supported by the observation that long distance *event quantification* comparatives are not possible (cf. (30)).

Hence, *event quantification* comparatives are another case of standards of comparison that do not conform to the [INDIVIDUAL]/[DEGREE] semantic parameter proposed in the literature. As was the case for *more N than N comparatives* presented in Section 2.2., *event quantification* comparatives do not involve a directly degree-denoting standard (there is no degree abstraction, as evidenced by the lack of subject-verb inversion in the standard clause and the lack of a long distance event interpretation) and they are not individual-denoting standards either. This means that we need to modify the semantic parameter in order to account for the variation observed in these standards of comparison.

Following the logic of the syntactic parameter presented in Section 1.1, I would like to propose a *semantic parameter* that distinguishes directly degree-denoting standards -- that is, those standards of comparison that present a MP or involve some kind of degree abstraction (*wh*-movement or a degree relative clause) and are thus [+ DEGREE] denoting - from standards that do not denote degrees directly and which will be represented as [- DEGREE] denoting.

The new classification of Spanish comparatives I propose is given in Table 2 and is based on two independent parameters: a syntactic parameter [-/+ CLASUAL] and a revised semantic parameter [-/+ DEGREE].

		SYNTACTIC	
		- CLAUSAL	+ CLAUSAL
SEMANTIC	- DEGREE	Spanish (<i>que</i> phrasal)	Spanish (<i>que</i> event quantif.)
	+ DEGREE	QP or amount RC	<i>wh</i> -movement
		Spanish (<i>de</i>)	Spanish (<i>que</i> subcomparative)

Table 2: Parametric variation on the expression of standards of comparison in Spanish

3. Analysis

Following the work by Bartsch & Vennemann (1972) or Kennedy (1999), among others, in adjectival comparatives I assume a measure function analysis of gradable predicates, as in (35).

$$(35) \llbracket \text{tall}_{\mu} \langle e, d \rangle \rrbracket = \lambda x. \text{tall}(x)$$

In nominal comparatives, *more* is analysed as an analytic comparative marker consisting of the quantity word *many* and the comparative marker, following Bresnan (1973), as illustrated in (36).

$$(36) \text{ more} = \mu + \text{er}$$

Following the counting function analysis of the quantity word *many* proposed for English (cf. Schwarzschild 2006, Kennedy 2002, 2007, Rett forth., Solt 2015, a.o.), I assume that in nominal comparatives Spanish *más* also includes a quantity word that behaves as a hybrid between a quantifier and a gradable predicate, represented as ‘ μ ’, as illustrated in (37).

$$(37) \llbracket \mu \langle et, d \rangle \rrbracket = \lambda X. \mu(X)$$

With these premises in mind, a novel formal analysis of Spanish inequality comparatives is presented in Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 that accounts for the syntactic and semantic properties examined in Section 2.

3.1. Spanish: *de* standards

De standards in Spanish take either a MP or a degree relative clause (cf. Sáez 1992, Grosu & Landman 1998, Gutiérrez-Rexach 1999). Following the proposed parameters, these standards are [+ DEGREE] denoting in the semantics and have a [- CLAUSAL] structure.

- (38) a. Ana compró más libros de *los que ves ahí*.
 Ana bought more books than the that see there
 ‘Ana bought more books than_{de} you see there.’
- b. Ana compró más libros de [QP los [~~μ -libros~~]_i [CP [~~μ -libros~~]_i que *pro*_{you} ves ahí [~~μ -libros~~]_i]].^{12,13}
 ‘Ana bought more books than [QP the [~~μ -books~~]_i [CP [~~μ -books~~]_i that *pro*_{you} see there [~~μ -books~~]_i]].’

Following McConnell-Ginet’s (1973) idea that all inequality comparatives involve the presence of a gap - that is, the difference between the two compared values, which equals a set of degrees or an interval (cf. Schwarzschild & Wilkinson 2002, Schwarzschild 2005) - *más libros de los que ves ahí* in (38) would have the denotation in (39).¹⁴

$$(39) \llbracket \text{más } N \text{ de } d \rrbracket = \lambda\mu \lambda P \lambda d \exists X \exists I [P(X) \ \& \ I = \mu(X) - d \ \& \ I \subseteq (0, +\infty)]$$

The observation that *de* comparatives in Spanish are closely related to magnitudes has always been present in traditional grammars of Spanish. The representation in (39) of *más de* comparatives supposes a novel approach to the formalization of that long-standing observation. See also Mendia (forth.) for independent evidence in favor of the degree-denoting analysis of *más de* comparatives.

3.2. Spanish: *que* standards with coordination

The data examined in Section 2 appeals to a distinction between two main types of *que* standards. In particular:

- A. Conjunctive *que*, which introduces [- DEGREE] denoting standards that can be either [-CLAUSAL] or [+CLAUSAL].
- B. Prepositional *que*, which introduces [+ DEGREE] denoting and [+CLAUSAL] standards.

Those standards that are non-directly degree-denoting [- DEGREE] involve a coordinated structure (Sáez 1992). In these cases, I propose that a measuring function (either the gradable predicate or a μ counting function) is applied to both coordinates to obtain the degree argument that sets the standard of comparison. In the English phrasal version of example (15),

¹² Sáez (1992), Grosu & Landman (1998) and Gutiérrez-Rexach (1999), a.o., offer different analyses for degree relatives. The comparison of these three proposals goes beyond the scope of this paper. The reader is referred to these works for related discussion.

¹³ We can find examples where ‘ μ ’ seems to be explicit in sentences like (i) from the newspaper *Diario de León* (05/06/2013).

(i) Esto es un crimen más *de los muchos* que hay en este país.
 this is a crime more than the many that happen in this country
 ‘This is one more crime of (than_{de}) the many that happen in this country.’

¹⁴ The analysis of comparatives presented in this paper makes use of non-empty intervals to describe the difference between the compared elements. Nevertheless, nothing hinges on this particular approach to inequality comparatives, and a more traditional analysis in terms of a greater than (>) relation could also be applied in (39). However, the possibility of licensing a differential is one of the main features that distinguishes inequality comparatives from other comparatives and degree constructions. The application of an analysis in terms of intervals of difference highlights the importance of this crucial component of inequality comparatives.

repeated below as (40), a function from plural objects to degrees of cardinality (μ) is applied to both coordinates, i.e. *women* and *men*. A schematic structure is proposed in (41), and (42) to illustrate its semantic representation.

More N than N: nominal coordination in a comparative structure

(40) More women than men attended the march.

(41) [-er [μ women] than [μ men]] attended the march.

(42) $\exists X \exists Y \exists I$ [women(X) & men(Y) & $I = \mu(X) - \mu(Y)$ & $I \subseteq (0, +\infty)$]
There are some X, some Y and an interval I, such that X are women and Y are men, and the number of men minus the number of women equals a non-empty interval (a set of degrees).

In clausal standards, following a neo-Davidsonian quantificational representation of events, the sentence in (22a), repeated below in (43), would be assigned the representation in (44). I leave the specifics on the syntactic structure of *event quantification* comparatives such as (43) for future research.

Event quantification comparatives:

(43) Jon compró más libros que Ana leyó cómics.¹⁵
Jon bought more books than Ana read comics
'Jon bought more books than_{que} Ana read comics.'

(44) There is an event e_1 , whose sub-events consist of book-buyings by Jon, and another event e_2 , whose sub-events are comic-readings by Ana, and the number of e_1 sub-events minus the number of e_2 sub-events equals a non-empty interval.

3.3. Spanish: que subcomparatives

Clausal standards introduced by *que* in which the subject and the verb of the embedded clause are inverted involve a degree abstraction operation with *wh*-movement (Sáez 1992, Bruccart 2003). Consequently, I classify *subcomparatives* as being [+ DEGREE] [+ CLAUSAL].

In particular, I defend that the standard of comparison in Spanish *subcomparatives* presented in (22b/45) behaves similarly to that of a free relative clause (cf. Sáez 1992) in the sense that it denotes a maximal degree. Consequently, despite their syntactic differences, *subcomparatives* and comparatives where the standard is introduced by the preposition *de* are similar in that, in both cases, *más* takes a degree-denoting standard of comparison, as proposed in (39) and illustrated in (46).

(45) a. Jon compró más libros que cómics leyó Ana.

¹⁵ As a reviewer kindly indicates, frequency comparatives in English as in sentence (i) appear similar to the Spanish [- DEGREE, + CLAUSAL] event quantification comparatives:

(i) John buys books more than Mary reads comics.

I leave the examination and comparison of English examples like (i) with Spanish comparatives like (22a) for further research.

- Jon bought more books than comics read Ana
 ‘Jon bought more books than Ana read comics.’
- b. Jon compró más libros que [_{CP} [μ cómics]_i leyó Ana t_i].
 ‘Jon bought more books than [_{CP} [μ comics]_i read Ana t_i].’

$$(46) \llbracket \text{más } N \text{ que } d_{\text{subcomparative}} \rrbracket = \lambda\mu \lambda P \lambda d \exists X \exists I [P(X) \ \& \ I = \mu(X) - d \ \& \ I \subseteq (0, +\infty)]$$

3.4. Cross-linguistic perspective

The main questions that this paper addresses are the following: how can we derive a compositional analysis that accounts for the syntactic and semantic properties of standards of comparison? And what are the constraints that apply to standards of comparison cross-linguistically?

The recent literature on standards of comparison establishes the locus of cross-linguistic variation in a syntactic *phrasal vs. clausal structure* distinction, and a semantic *individual-denoting vs. degree-denoting* distinction.

Looking at data from Spanish comparatives, I have shown that the proposed semantic *individual/degree* parameter of variation is insufficient to account for the observed data in Spanish, and a refinement on this parameter has been proposed.

Specifically, I have shown several examples of standards of comparison which are not (i) degree-denoting (that is, the standard of comparison does not include a phrasal structure with a MP or a degree relative clause, nor a clausal structure with degree abstraction); nor (ii) individual-denoting. For this reason, the semantic parameter has been redefined as a [-/+ DEGREE] parameter, that distinguishes directly degree-denoting standards [+ DEGREE] from standards that do not denote degrees directly [- DEGREE], which can denote individuals, properties or events, for example.

Furthermore, I have proposed an analysis where, in order to obtain the degree that establishes the referent for the comparison in [- DEGREE] denoting standards, a measure function (a gradable predicate or a counting function *many* or *much*) is applied to the element in the standard of comparison.

In sum, in order to answer the main questions discussed in this paper, I have proposed that standards of comparison cross-linguistically can be classified with respect to two independent parameters: a syntactic one [-/+ CLAUSAL] and a semantic one [-/+ DEGREE]. *Table 3* illustrates the parametric variation on the expression of standards of comparison with some sample languages. The cross-linguistic data for this classification has been collected from Hofstetter (2009), for Turkish; Sudo (2015), for Japanese; Heim (1985) and Kennedy (1999), for English; and Donati (1997) and Belletti (1991-1995), for Italian. The classification of Spanish comparatives has been implemented according the analysis presented in Section 3. The classification of Basque comparatives is a tentative approach to describe standards of comparison in this language. Nevertheless, a deeper analysis of comparatives in this language is still necessary.

		SYNTACTIC	
		- CLAUSAL	+ CLAUSAL
SEMANTIC	- DEGREE	Turkish (ABL), Japanese (yori), Basque (baino), English (than), Italian (che), Spanish (que)	Spanish (que), Italian (che)
	+ DEGREE	QP or amount RC Turkish (ABL), Japanese (yori), Basque (baino), English (than), Italian (di), Spanish (de)	wh-movement English (than), Spanish (que _{inversion}), Italian (di _{inversion})

Table 3: Parametric classification of standards of comparison

This novel parametric classification should improve our understanding of cross-linguistic variation of inequality comparatives, as well as setting up the basis for a compositional analysis of comparative structures.

4. Conclusion

In order to elaborate accounts of comparative structures as a whole, a deeper understanding of the individual pieces that compose the puzzle that comparatives represent is necessary. With this goal in mind, I have focused on one of the main components of these structures: the standard of comparison.

Two independent parameters have been argued to be necessary to account for the properties of standards of comparison cross-linguistically: a syntactic one [-/+ CLAUSAL], and a semantic one [-/+ DEGREE] denoting. In particular, Spanish standards of comparison can be classified into three types:

- A) Phrasal *de* standards that take either a MP or a degree relative clause as their complement and denote degrees [+ DEGREE] [- CLAUSAL];
- B) *Que* standards that involve coordinated structures and are not directly degree-denoting [- DEGREE]. These can be either [- CLAUSAL] or [+ CLAUSAL];
- C) Clausal *que* standards with subject-verb inversion in the standard clause that involve (*wh*) operator movement and denote degrees [+ DEGREE] [+ CLAUSAL].

Finally, the Spanish data also supports those analyses which argue that the comparative meaning depends both on the comparative marker (*más*) and the standard marker (*que* or *de*).

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